

Experimental insights into PEG based new fluids thermal effusivity

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Abstract. Fluids thermal transfer is of utmost relevance in a large number of industrial or semi industrial applications. On the other hand, the need for environmental friendly new fluids plays a relevant role in the heat transfer agent selection. Poly(ethylene glycol) are synthetic, hydrophilic, biocompatible polymers with extensive use in a large number of applications. PEGs are synthesized by means of a ring-opening polymerization of ethylene oxide and a large range of molecular weights and polydispersity's are produced. From these products, only substances with lower molecular weights can be employed for thermal transfer., more exactly for molecular weight lower than 600. This paper presents the outcomes of an experimental investigation into the thermal effusivity of PEG 400, PEG 200 and water mixtures for convection heat transfer applications. Quite a lot of samples with different concentrations were manufactured, examined and the data were thoroughly discussed comparatively and in the context of cutting-edge advancements. The concept now known as thermal effusivity has been employed since the early stages of heat transfer research as a valuable feature for analyzing 1D heat transfer setups.

Introduction

Nowadays there is an imperious need to discover and study new heat transfer fluids, especially for applications beyond water evaporation point. There is a tremendous need for new fluids to be implemented at medium temperatures (i.e. larger than 80 – 100 °C). Several candidates for these temperatures are polyethylene glycols (PEG), that serves as a defoaming agent, lubricant, and viscosity modifier in a variety of products. PEGs are not a new material, but their mixtures and applications can be further studied (see [1] for further details).

PEGs, together with chemicals as paraffin and fatty acid, are organic phase change materials with a uniform phase transformation and reasonable nucleation frequency [2]. Basically, PEGs are polyether composite with immeasurable usages, from engineering to medical applications. Their structure is $H-(O-CH_2-CH_2)_n-OH$, while their usages are:

- Various chemical applications (including use as a lubricant, in biochemistry or biomembrane experimental studies, as a surfactant, and as a calibration substance in mass spectrometry, among others);
- Medicine (utilized as an excipient, for instance);
- Biology (used as a crowding agent for protein crystallization)
- Commercial applications (for instance, in tattoos to monitor diabetes, as an anti-foaming agent in various food and beverage products, in skin creams, and as a dispersant in toothpaste)
- Industrial uses (employed as an anti-foaming agent, in technical ceramics, and as an insulator)
- Recreational applications.

The name PEG is followed by a numerical value that represents the average molecular weight. An in-depth discussion on these aspects is outlined in Minea [1], together with an outline of PEGs thermophysical properties at room temperature.

Summarizing, Poly(ethylene glycol) is a synthetic, hydrophilic, biocompatible polymer with extensive use. This paper will be focused on low mass PEGs, as for example POEG 200 and PEG 400 and several mixtures. These two polymers are mixtures of molecules with varying sizes that differ in the number of oxyethylene units, having average molecular weights of 200 and 400, respectively.

Research results for different PEG based fluids are ongoing and several authors (see [3-11]) studied low mass compounds for different thermophysical properties, outlining these fluids relevance for heat transfer applications.

PEG-200 offers a diverse array of potential applications and can be employed as defoaming agent, lubricant or viscosity converter in several applications. PEG-200 can additionally be utilized as a coating for fresh produce, a solvent in metalworking fluids, a binder and modifier in paint formulations, and as a humectant in both inks and abrasives [1, 2, 10]. Another important feature is that PEG 200 is environmentally friendly, which is a great quality nowadays, when special preoccupation on environmental issues is mandatory. Plus, PEG 200 is completely soluble in water and has an average molecular weight ranging from 190 to 210 (see Fig.1 for the chemical structure).

On the other hand, PEG 400 shares mostly the same features as PEG 200, having a larger molar mass (i.e. around 400) [3-9, 11].

Figure 1. Chemical structure of PEG 200

This research is focused on PEG 200, PEG 400 and their several mixtures as the base fluids for heat transfer applications. Results were discussed in terms of thermal effusivity as a good indication for heat transfer behaviour, being one of the most relevant parameters when it discusses phase change materials applications and performances.

Experimental

Several fluids were manufactured using water, PEG 200 and PEG 400 as base. The substance were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA) and the suspensions were manufactured as are identified in Table 1 and Table 2, using different mole fractions. For fluids manufacturing, the chemicals were measured on a KERN ADJ 100-4 balance (Kern, Germany), which provides an accuracy of 1 mg. Further, the new fluids, as well as the pure fluids (see Table 1) were tested using the C-Therm Trident Thermal Conductivity System (C-Therm, USA) is equipped with a Basic-k Module featuring a Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) sensor, in accordance with ASTM D7984. The equipment measures thermal effusivity with a precision of 0.999, as per manufacturer indications. Thermal effusivity testing has been standardized by ASTM International (American

Society for Testing and Materials), and C-Therm incorporated stringent procedures and experimental parameters to ensure the highest accuracy in measuring thermal effusivity.

The experimental data were collected at ambient temperature, since previous research demonstrated that there is minor variation when temperature rises (see Chereches et al. [12, 13])

Table 1. Manufactured fluids

Fluid	Code	PEG 200 mass in mixture [g]	PEG 400 mass in mixture [g]	Water mass [g]	Total mass [g]
distilled water	W	-	-	10	10
PEG 400	F0				
PEG 200	F1	7.5144	-	-	7.5144
0.75 PEG200+0.25 PEG400	F2	7.5214	5.0149	-	12.5363
0.5 PEG200+0.5 PEG400	F3	3.7619	7.52	-	11.2819
0.25 PEG200+0.75 PEG400	F4	1.495	9.0318	-	10.5268
0.25 PEG200+0.75 water	F5	7.502	-	2.0181	9.5201

Table 2. Fluids composition

Fluid	PEG 200		PEG 400		Water	
	mass fraction[-]	mole fraction[-]	mass fraction[-]	mole fraction[-]	mass fraction[-]	mole fraction[-]
distilled water	-	-	-	-	1	1
PEG 400	-	-	1	1	-	-
PEG 200	1	1	-	-	-	-
0.75 PEG200+0.25 PEG400	0.6	0.75	0.4	0.25	-	-
0.5 PEG200+0.5 PEG400	0.34	0.5	0.67	0.5	-	-
0.25 PEG200+0.75 PEG400	0.14	0.25	0.85	0.76	-	-
0.25 PEG200+0.75 water	0.79	0.25	-	-	0.21	0.75

The experimental setup assures the best collection of data for the investigated samples, as was recommended by the C-Therm training in using the equipment and C-Therm software for gathering data. Data was collected at ambient temperature, while C-Therm software register both the temperature, as well as thermal effusivity values.

Experimental accuracy is calculated as 0.1 % for mass weighting and maximum 0.01 % at thermal effusivity tests, as is calculated by the C-Therm software. The software calculates the R-squared value in comparison with a test sample, as is depicted in the C-Therm documentation.

Results and discussion

Firstly, the thermal effusivity of base fluids was measured, followed by the new fluids investigation.

The experimental results are described in Fig. 2, where the influence of the components can be observed. The thermal effusivity accuracy is $R^2 = 0.99$, as was measured by the equipment for each data set. Several measurements were achieved for each sample and the results are averaged. Basically, thermal effusivity reflects a material's capacity to exchange heat with its immediate environment at a surface, and it is expressed as:

$$e = \sqrt{k\rho c_p} \quad (1)$$

Here, e represents thermal effusivity, k denotes thermal conductivity, ρ indicates density, and c_p refers to mass specific heat capacity.

Fig. 2 shows the experimental points for each fluid and is noticed that the higher value was measured for distilled water, while PEGs and their mixtures registered lower thermal effusivity and this is normal, since the thermal conductivity of PEGs is lower than the one of water. Plus, there is a correspondence between the thermal effusivity of each component and the one registered for the mixture.

On the other hand, the data were compared with the rule of mixture, which is mostly applied for all fluidic mixtures between two immiscible components. The rule of mixture for most of the properties, except viscosity, which follows Arrhenius law can be outlined as:

$$e_{\text{mixture}} = (N_1 \cdot e_1) + (N_2 \cdot e_2) \quad (2)$$

Where e is the thermal effusivity, mixture refers to the mixture property, while N is the molar fraction.

The results are comparatively plotted in Fig. 3 where it can notice that the rule of mixtures does not apply to thermal effusivity. The deviation was higher for the mixture PEG 200 + distilled water (62.39 %), while for the two PEGs mixture the variation lies into $-0.01 - 1.36$ %. An observation arises that, when two similar fluids are mixed, the rule of mixtures can successfully estimate the thermal effusivity of the new compound.

Fig. 2 Thermal effusivity experimental results

If it looks to Fig. 3 it can say that the rule of mixture can predict the thermal effusivity of the mixture between the two PEGs with a good precision. On the other hand, when it add water to PEG, the experimental thermal effusivity of the mixture is lesser than the one calculated. In this situation, a pattern needs to be observed and more experimental is necessary to be developed in order to set an experimental correlation.

In the next lines, also thermal diffusivity will be discussed for the developed fluids Thermal diffusivity, measured in m^2/s , is calculated by dividing thermal conductivity (k) by the product of density (ρ) and specific heat capacity at constant pressure (c_p). It offers important insights into the heat transfer processes occurring within the fluid. The equation writes as:

$$a = k/\rho c_p \tag{3}$$

The results on thermal diffusivity are depicted in Table 3, where the data were calculated based on thermal effusivity and density of all liquids and mixtures.

The density of a mixture from two liquids is the resulting density of the mixture formed when two liquids are mixed and is represented as:

$$\rho_{mixture} = (M_{mixture}) / \left(\frac{M_1}{\rho_1} + \frac{M_2}{\rho_2} \right) \tag{4}$$

Where ρ is the density, mixture refers to the mixture property, while M is the mass of each liquid or mixture, respectively.

Fig. 3 Comparison with rule of mixture

Table 3 Data on thermal diffusivity

	PEG 200 mole fraction	PEG 400 (or water for F5) mole fraction	Thermal diffusivity [m ² /s]
water distilled	-	-	1.49E-07
PEG 400 – F0	-	-	9.49E-08
PEG 200 - F1	-	-	9.5E-08
F2	0.75	0.25	9.5E-08
F3	0.5	0.5	9.49E-08
F4	0.25	0.75	9.49E-08
F5	0.25	0.75	9.9E-08

From Table 3 data it can conclude that all the PEGs and their mixtures have similar behavior at heat transfer, while water and F5 possess better features in terms of thermal transport. However, it needs to outline here that the W and F5 fluids are suitable for temperatures up to 90 °C, while the PEGs and their mixture can support temperatures up to 200 °C.

As a prospectus, these authors can suggest several ways to increase the thermal effusivity, thus heat transfer behavior by using the concept of nanofluid. In these conditions, the addition of solid high conductive nanoparticles can improve the heat transfer compartment. Nevertheless, this method needs to be carefully studied and debated in order to control the drawbacks of an increased viscosity or sedimentation occurrence, that will affect the flow behavior and increase the pumping power.

Conclusion

Several mixtures based on polyethylene glycol were manufactured and the thermal effusivity was experimentally measured. Results indicated that the effusivity of the mixture depend on the

compound, while the rule of mixture cannot predict the values of different chemicals mixture. The experiment outcomes can be summarized as:

- Water thermal effusivity is higher than that of PEGs
- PEG 200 and PEG 400 thermal effusivity depends on their molar mass
- PEG 200 has larger thermal effusivity than that of PEG 400, while all the mixtures have values between the two PEGs
- The mixture between PEG 200 and distilled water has an increased thermal effusivity, being strongly influenced by the water addition.
- The thermal diffusivity of all mixtures is lower than that of water

As a general conclusion, it may say that, even if the water addition increases the heat transfer capacity, the applications are different in terms of temperature, while PEGs area of application is beyond water boiling point. Finally, the addition of nanoparticles to PEG based fluids can be a solution to increase the thermal effusivity and further experimental insights are mandatory.

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